

The Physiological Effect of Newcastle Diseses on Blood Parameter Antioxidant Enzymes, Feed Consumption and Weight of Chicken

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Abstract:

The aim of the current study was to identify the physiological effect of Newcastle disease in infected bird comparing with healthy bird .in these experiment 60 bird were divided into two groups each group was two replicates .The group of control T (healthy bird) the group T1 (infected bird).The blood sample was collected in the end of the experiment the measure of hemoglobin (Hb) ,Total leukocyte cell count (TLC) , Total erythrocyte count (TEC), Differentiation white blood cell, Total protein, Globulin ,and antioxidant enzymes Glutathione peroxidase (GSH-XP), Catalase (CAT) ,Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Malondialdehyde (MDA). and we were measured the production parameters like a verge of weight, a verge of feed

consumption rate and the rate of food conversion efficiency. The results show that significant $p \leq 0.05$ affected of the healthy bird compared with infected bird in most of the measure .This confirms that infected with Newcastle disease effect on the physiology of blood and antioxidant so his loss occurs in production of chickens that did not die in the field and this lead to major economic loss .

Keywords: *Newcastle dieses, chicken, blood parameter, antioxidant, production.*

Introduction

Newcastle Disease also known as pseudo fowl plague, it was caused avian *paramyxo virus* serotype 1 (APMV-1). That can effect a large number of avian species and cause severe economic losses The disease can infected more than two hundred different species of bird (Rauw, et al., 2009). This disease effect on intracerebral pathogen city index (ICPI) in day old chickens of 0.7 (OIE, 2018). The first outbreak of Newcastle disease occurred in 1926 in Java and also described in Korea in the same year (Kranefeld, 1926) .All Newcastle disease are

member of APMV-1 and it have some serotype it noted that there was genetic and anti-genetic diversity in different genotypes (Miller, & Koch, 2013). The analysis of Newcastle disease virus genome explained there was three genome sizes divided into two classes I and II (Courteny, et al., 2012). Class I contains a virulent strains of the virus with a genome size of 1598 nucleotides, while class II contain both virulent and a virulent strains with genomes size 1586 or 1592 nucleotides .There are 9 genotypes within class I and 18 genotypes within class II (Diel. et al., 2012). Newcastle disease virus is capable of infecting more than 200 different species of

poultry (Rauw, et al., 2009). The infection has been established in 241 bird species representing 27 orders of the bird classes chickens are the most species and then Turkey, Wild bird. Pigeons are infected with a Pigeons paramixovirus (PPMV) (Alexander, 2000). The disease can be transmitted to healthy poultry thru direct contact by ingestion or inhalation or secretion from the respiratory tract or by indirect contact transmission by contaminated feed, water and by workers clothes and shoes (Komlan, & Balabadi, 2021). The clinical signs and severity of the disease depend on the type of the causative strain whether it is high virulent or low virulent (Alexander, et al., 2012). It is also depending on the age of the bird as it affects the completeness of the immune system as well as the method of transmitting of infection to infected birds, the incubation period 2-15 day in average 5-6 day. The clinical signs of the disease like Watery discharge from eyes, conjunctivitis, cough, sneezing, Gaspings, low egg production, greenish diarrhea, paralysis of leg and wings later droopy wings and lameness, high rate of mortality and morbidity, swelling of head and torticollis neck and spasms (Abdisa, & Tagesu, 2017). The current vaccines are not effective enough to prevent viral shedding and infection of vaccinated bird. The vaccine strains where the effectiveness of breeds used in vaccines and long periods of time tolerant about the effectiveness of this bird in developing at the progress of time in the successive years (Mustapha, et al., 2023). The vaccine of Newcastle disease have two types Live-virus vaccine are mostly common used because it is expensive produce and Killed – virus (inactivated vaccines) use the killed virus these vaccine was more costly to produce and administer because of the high antigenic need to induce a good immune response vaccine administering via drinking water, aerosol, and it also can administrate individually directly vaccination in the eye of a bird or by beakdipping (Senne, King, & Kapczynski, 2004).

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the field of meat chickens a private sector in Babylon governorate, Iraq. For period of 1/9-10/10/2023 60 chick were used Belgian Ross breed in age 1 day with an average weight of 45g the field was struck by Newcastle disease. It was randomly distributed to 2 treatments with two replicates for each treatments and 15 chick for each replicate (30 treated chick in one treatment).

The first group T was control (chick healthy and not infected) second group T1 (chick infected with Newcastle disease).

Collect Blood Samples

Blood samples were collected from infected and healthy birds obtained from the jugular vein and kept in laboratory tubes, some of them with an anticoagulant and others without. From each sample, the serum was extracted and centrifuged. The blood cells were then separated from the serum. The serum applied to antioxidant enzyme examination, total protein, Globulins and the blood with anticoagulant tube used for examination of, total leukocyte count (TLC) 1, differential count white blood cell, total erythrocyte count (TEC), hemoglobin (Hb). The production characteristics were weekly determined by feed consumption rate, weight, and food conversion efficiency according to the equation given below:

Food conversion = Amount of feed consumed in certain period weight gain during the same period the complete random design (CRD) was applied to analyze the results using the Statistical software SAS (edition, 2001).

Statistical Analysis

Table 1. Presents of the Diet Composition and the Analysis of its Nutritional Value.

	Ingredient and analysis	(%) 1-21 day	(%) 22- 42 day
1	Corn	56.0	61.9
2	Soybean meal	29.5	21.7

3	Concentrated portion	10.0	10
4	Vegetable oil	2.5	4.5
5	Ground limestone	0.7	0.8
6	salt	0.3	0.4
7	Dicalcium phosphate	1.0	0.7
Chemical analysis			
1	Energy	3000 KCl	3104 KCl
2	Protein	22.6	20
3	Methionine %	0.60	0.56
4	Lysine %	1.56	1.36
5	Calcium	1.12	1.12
6	Phosphorus	0.42	0.42

Note: NRC (15)

Results and Discussion

Blood Characteristics

The result in Table 2 showed that there was significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in TEC, Hb, Hetrophil, Monocyte, Eosinophil, Basophiles. in T group compared with T1 and there is significant ($p < 0.05$) TLC, Lymphocyte, Total protein, Globulin in T1 compared with T group. The results are approved for the mention (Malik, et al., 2018) the ND affected chickens may be it is because possible loss of blood from

hemorrhages proventriculus, gastrointestinal tract ulcers, and also due to intravascular hymolysis (Chekwube, et al., 2014). In infection the level of different types of white blood cells are elevated because it play a role in all viral and bacterial infections and the total protein and globulin (Harrison, et al., 2011). The Newcastle disease was cause elevation in total proteins and globulins due to the inflammation effect and the activity of B Lymphocyte this is response to immune system work and increase in immune globulin in viral infection (Philips, et al., 2015).

Table 2. The Hematological Effect of Newcastle Disease in TEC, TLC, Hb, Total protein, Globulin, white Blood Cell Types.

Parameter	T Un infected	T1 Infected
TEC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$)	3.0 \pm 0.9 a	2.01 \pm 0.8 b
TLC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	17.5 \pm 0.8 b	20.5 \pm 1.01 a
Hb (g/dl)	11.2 \pm 0.3 a	9.5 \pm 0.3 b
Total protein (g/dl)	2.8 \pm 0.08 b	3.9 \pm 0.6a
Globulin (g/dl)	1.63 \pm 0.07b	1.93 \pm 0.08a
Hetrophil (%) ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	27 \pm 0.02 a	18.5 \pm 0.03b
Lymphocyte (%) ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	63 \pm .2 b	74.5 \pm 0.15 a
Monocyte (%) ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	7 \pm 15 a	4 \pm 0.14 b
Eosinophil (%) ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	2 \pm 0.04 a	2.8 \pm 0.04a
Basophiles (%) ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{l}$)	1 \pm 0.03a	0.2 \pm 0.02 b

Note: The numbers represent the rates \pm standard error; The small letter means that there is significant difference at the level ($p < 0.05$).

Antioxidant Enzymes

The results shown in Table 3 indicate to the level of antioxidant enzymes there is significant ($p < 0.05$) in GSH-PX, CAT, SOD in control group according with T1 and there is significant

($p < 0.05$) in MDA in T1 group compared with control group the activity of immune system against diseases was causing increase in the level of (ROS) reactive oxygen species for the over production of (ROS) decreased antioxidant

defense that can result in oxidative damage of ND. (Serafini, & Del Rio, 2004), so that there is low level of antioxidant enzymes in T1 .and because the stress effect of the viral infection we

noted there is lowering in antioxidant enzymes parameters (Surai, 2016). The affected cells can produce excess of oxidative factors as a result of being destroyed by the virus (Surai, 2002).

Table 3. Effect Newcastle Disease in Gsh-px, CAT, S.O.D, M.D.A.

Parameter	T Un infected	T1 Infected
GSH-PX (IU/L)	190.3±0.23a	160.5±0.92b
CAT (IU/L)	150.5±0.02a	135.8±1.05b
SOD (IU/ml)	6.23±0.012a	4.2±0.021b
MDA (µM)	5.03±0.023b	9.2±0.072a

Note: The numbers represent the rates ± standard error; The small letter means that there is significant difference at the level (p<0.05).

Feed Consumption and Weight

The result of Table 4 revealed that a significant difference (p<0.05) in feed consumption weight gain in control group compared with T1 except feed conversion T1 there is significant in T1 compared with control group this result agree with (Wang, et al., 2015). Newcastle disease

cause gastro intestinal infection and it cause loss of appetite Greenish diarrhea and bleeding in the intestinal and cecum (Cattoli, et al., 2011). The stress in effected broiler was caused physiological effect it was lead to reduce the body weight gain and feed efficiency that result may be due to increase in corticosterone (Vinden, et al., 2007).

Table 4. Effect of Newcastle Disease in Feed Consumption, Weight Gain, Feed Conversion

Parameter	T Un infected	T1 Infected
feed consumption	990±3.23a	698±1.203b
weight gain	2001.5±.4a	1130±0.02b
feed conversion	0.494±0.01b	0.617±0.01a

Note: The numbers represent the rates ± standard error; The small letter means that there is significant difference at the level (p<0.05).

Conclusion

The study found that Newcastle disease (ND) in chickens causes significant changes in blood parameters, indicating a strong immune response and negative impact on overall health. Infected birds experienced lower erythrocyte and leukocyte counts, higher protein levels, and reduced feed consumption and weight gain. While non-lethal infections can still result in economic losses, effective vaccination and management strategies are crucial for mitigating the impact of ND on poultry populations. Future research should explore long-term effects of the disease and develop improved prevention and treatment methods.

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